

Impact of HRM Practices on Employee Productivity: A Study on the RMG Sector in Bangladesh

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Abstract:-

Purpose: RMG sector in Bangladesh is one of the fast growing sectors in the economy of Bangladesh that can be understood by analyzing its gradual contribution during the last few years (Khan and Ullah, 2017). However, this industry has some prospects as well as challenges since it is competing in the global marketplace. Developing the human capital in this sector is very much needed in this regard. The academics as well as practitioners in this industry are contributing through their research and development works. In this circumstance, human resource management of RMG factories has gained much importance from both academics and HR practitioners. Most of the researchers argue that HR practices have a significant contribution to the development of this sector. This study aims at exploring the impact of HR practices on employee productivity. Hopefully, the findings of this study will help the practitioners as well as future researchers to understand the value of HR practices on increasing employee productivity.

Methods: Descriptive study method has been used to conduct this study where a self-designed structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from the respondents (N=178) working in the RMG sector in Bangladesh. SPSS Version 20.0 has been used to analyze the collected primary data. However, face to face interviews with some HR professionals and top management of RMG industry have been conducted before designing questionnaires and while interpreting those. Besides primary data, this study also uses secondary data from different sources which have been acknowledged properly through both in-text citation and reference section.

Dimensions of HRM: This study uses six dimensions of HR practices which are Recruitment & Selection, HR Compliance, Compensation & Benefits, Performance Management, Employee Participation, and Training & Development as independent variables where employee productivity has been taken as a dependent variable.

Findings: This finds that all of the HR practices have significant impact on employee productivity. Particularly, it finds the highest correlation between compensation and benefits and employee productivity. It also finds the second highest correlation between HR compliance and employee productivity in the RMG sector in Bangladesh. However, all of the hypotheses of the study were accepted.

Keywords:- *Hrm Practices; Employee Productivity, Ready Made Garments (Rmg) Sector, Bangladesh.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Resource Management has gained research attention from both academics and practitioners of the area during the last decades. This area has been studied from different perspectives from time to time by different scholars. Firms are competing with each other using their resources and tools. To compete with other firms in this highly competitive market in the era of globalization, firms have identified human resource management as their source of competitive advantage (Pfeffer, 1995). People bring sustainable advantages to the organization through which organizations can obtain sustainable development (Nkogbu, 2015). Moreover, the RMG sector of Bangladesh is one of the fastest growing sectors of the economy of Bangladesh. The contribution of RMG makes it a vital area both for building a career and doing research. However, researchers' contribution in this sector especially in the perspective of HRM is very insignificant.

A very common question comes to the mind of people whether HR Practices have any effect on the performance of the organization. However, through different research it has been shown that there is a cause-effect relationship between Human Resource Management Practices and organization's performance (Wright et al, 2004). HR Practices have positive impacts on the financial performance of an organization since HR Practices provide competitive advantages to the organization that makes it different from other competitors in the market (Paauwe and Boselie, 2008).

To show the relationship between HR practices and organizational performance, Guest Model uses some mediating variables. Guest model shows a flow of relationship among HRM Strategy, HRM practices, HRM outcomes, Behavior Outcomes, Performance outcome and finally the financial outcomes (Guest 1997).

The link between innovation performance and HR practices has also been found and that innovation performance then leads to overall organizational performance (Laursen and Foss, 2003). Corporate financial performance is largely dependent on the effectiveness of HR Management (Huselid et al, 1997). Liu et al (2007) provide answers to a very common question- "Does Human Resource Management Matter?" and shows that HR practices are

linked to performance through three key channels which are a. increase employees KSAs, b. Motivate employees to leverage KSAs and c. Employer employees to do so (Liu et al 2007).

However, a significant number of researchers studies on the dimensions of human resource management practices and they explored the relationship between HRM Practices and different types of employee and organizational outcomes (Uzair et al., 2017; Nwachukwu and Chladkova, 2018; Aktar and Pangil, 2018))

Study shows significant positive relationship between some HR Practices (Independent variables) and efficient employee performance (Dependent variable) (Fatema, 2018) based on the healthcare sector of Bangladesh. Other than that different studies deal with HRM practices like HR planning, recruitment & selection, compensation and benefits, health safety & environment, employee motivation, employee engagement, employee participation, performance appraisal etc. and their impact on different organizational and individual outcomes like organizational performance, employee turnover, employee retention, job satisfaction, sales turnover etc. (Aybas and Acar, 2017; Piyasena and Kottawatta, 2015; Majumder, 2012).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Good number of studies regarding the impact of HRM practices on organizational performance have been conducted around the world. But in Bangladesh, this type of study is not so common, especially these types of studies are rare in the context of the RMG sector of Bangladesh. Moreover, most of the previous studies do not cover the HRM practices (Recruitment & Selection, HR Compliance, Compensation & Benefits, Performance Management, Employee Participation, and Training & Development) and their impact on employee productivity in the RMG sector in Bangladesh. This study focuses on exploring the impact of some selected HRM practices on employee productivity in the context of the RMG sector.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The broad objective of this study is to explore the impact of HRM practices on the employee productivity in the RMG sector of Bangladesh. However, along with the broad objective, this study covers some specific objectives too which have been listed below.

- To understand the impact of HRM practices on Employee Productivity in RMG sector
- To examine the individual impact of Recruitment & Selection, HR Compliance, Compensation & Benefits, Performance Management, Employee Participation, and Training & Development on employee productivity

To identify the activities having the highest impact and making recommendations for the HR practitioners of the RMG sector in Bangladesh regarding the importance of HR practices in increasing employee productivity.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies on human resource management are very common around the world. Because of the growing importance of HRM, it has attained the attention of the scholars since its inception as a branch of study (Lengnick-Hall and Lengnick-Hall, 1988). Some of the works have been studied for the purpose of conducting the current research that has been discussed according to the following sections.

A. HRM Practices

Human resource management is the art and science of managing the people of an organization that aims at attracting, developing, retaining and motivating the required number of human talent for carrying out the organizational activities (Aybas, and Acar, 2017; Tiwari and Tiwari, 2018; Gulzar, 2017; Nkogbu, 2015)). HRM practices cover the activities done under the human resource management like human resource planning, recruitment & selection, training & development, compensation & benefits, HR compliance, HR analytics, employee relations, talent management, knowledge management etc. (Ganapathy et al, 2018; Sung and Choi, 2014). Research on HRM practices focuses on its dimensions, importance, impact, relationship with other variables etc. (Raineri, 2016). This study is concerned with the following mentioned six dimensions of HR practice and their impact on employee productivity in the RMG sector in Bangladesh. So the literature has been reviewed accordingly in order to identify the real scenario.

➤ Recruitment & Selection

Recruitment & selection is one of the most important and frequently studied HRM practices. Recruitment & selection refers to the process of attracting and selecting human required human capital for the organization (Elearn, 2009; Lepisto and Ihtola, 2018). Researchers have been conducted on recruitment & selection from different angles. Researches on recruitment & selection mention it as one of the most valued activities since the performance of other HR activities are directly or indirectly dependent on it (Yaseen, 2016). Most of the research on this area covered the methods of recruitment and selection (Basaka and Khanna, 2017), the challenges of recruitment & selection (Marie Ryan and Derous, 2016), relationship between recruitment & selection with organizational and/or individual performance (Ahmad and Schroeder, 2002). Most of the researches find positive relationship between recruitment & selection and other organizational and/or individual employee performance (Gulzar, 2017), however, no research has been found in the context of RMG sector of Bangladesh showing its impact on employee productivity (Aker and Kamrul Alam, 2016).

➤ HR Compliance

HR compliance is regarded as an activity that is concerned with conforming the HR functions to laws, rules, policies, code of conduct and other principles to be followed (Khan, Arafin and Hossain, 2017). In the RMG sector of Bangladesh, most of the HR professionals are basically concerned with maintaining the compliance of HR activities with the requirement of different internal and external parties like government, buyers, trade union, chamber of commerce,

owners, buyers, suppliers and so on (Akter and Kamrul Alam, 2016). Very few studies have been found in this area. However, most studies on HR compliance discuss its nature, importance, evolution, impact and so forth (Ahamed, 2013). Moreover, no research has been found showing its impact on employee productivity in the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

➤ *Compensation & Benefits*

Compensation and benefits are the monetary and non-monetary payments paid to the employees in return to their contribution to the organizations (Hrcouncil.ca. 2018; Milkovich, 2011). Compensation & benefits (C&B) has been established as one of the branches of human resource management (Kang and Shen, 2017). Most of the study on C&B covers the topic like nature, types, impact on organizational performance (Ansary and Barua, 2015), link to employee motivation, link to job satisfaction (Rayton, 1996) etc. This study intends to examine the relationship between compensation & benefits and employee productivity in the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

➤ *Performance Management*

Performance management is the process of managing the performance of the employees of an organization in order to compensate and promote them accordingly (Aguinis, 2014). Most of the studies in this area cover performance appraisal which is basically a part of performance management (Kampkotter, 2016). Study shows that performance management has a significant relationship with organizational performance (Ahmed, Bin Ahmad and Raihan Joarder, 2016), productivity, job satisfaction (Ismail and Gali, 2016) etc. However, most of the studies conducted in this area cover different sectors like banking, SMEs, Telecommunication, NGOs etc. (DeNisi, and Murphy, 2017). This study intends to explore the relationship between performance management and employee productivity in the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

➤ *Employee Participation*

Employee participation refers to the process of ensuring participation of employees in the decision making process of the organization (Lower, 2010). Scholars suggested that employee participation is closely linked to the attainment of organizational objectives (Irawanto, 2015). Researches on employee participation cover different perspectives like its importance, dimensions, linkage to performance, linkage to job satisfaction etc. (Ahmed, Bin Ahmad and Raihan Joarder, 2016). However, very few studies have been found on employee participation in the context of the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

➤ *Training & Development*

Training & development refers to the programs run by the employers in order to prepare the employees for fulfilling the present and growing future needs of the organization (Noe, 2016). T&D basically focuses on developing the human talent as per the requirement of the organization in order to compete with other firms in the industry. Research on this area suggests that it has a positive impact on innovation and employee performance that leads to organizational performance (Ravi et al, (2017). Training & development is one of the widely studied parts of human

resource management. Studies on training & development cover the topics like methods, types, importance as well as its relationship with some organizational and individual outcomes (Falola et al, 2014). Furthermore, most of the scholars working on this area mention training & development as an investment for the organization where there is possibility of unlimited return (Dearden et al, 2005)). However, the current study aims at exploring the impact of training & development on employee productivity in the context of the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

B. Employee Productivity

Employee productivity is the assessment of the effectiveness and efficiency of the worker or a group of workers during a specific period of time (Miller, 1995). Employee productivity is directly linked to organizational productivity and performance (C. L. and M., 2016). At the same time, employee productivity depends on certain things like organizational support, availability of resources, organizational climate, technology, and HR practices (Ahamed, 2013). Researchers in the field of HR practices found a significant relationship between HRM practice and employee productivity, however, this study intends to understand the impact of some specific human resource management practices on employee productivity. In this study, employee productivity has been identified as the only dependent variable.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this study, the following conceptual framework has been constructed that shows the positive impact of HRM Practice (Recruitment & Selection, HR Compliance, Compensation & Benefits, Performance Management, Employee Participation, and Training & Development) on employee productivity.

Fig 01: Conceptual Framework

VI. HYPOTHESES

The questionnaire of the study has been designed based on some hypotheses. The hypotheses have been made based on six specific HR practices namely Recruitment & Selection, HR Compliance, Compensation & Benefits, Performance Management, Employee Participation, and Training & Development. The following are the hypotheses of this study.

- H1: Recruitment & Selection has a significant impact on employee productivity of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.
- H2: HR Compliance has a significant positive impact on employee productivity of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.
- H3: Compensation & Benefits has a significant impact on employee productivity of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.
- H4: Performance Management has a significant impact on employee productivity of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.
- H5: Employee Participation has a significant impact on employee productivity of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.
- H6: Training & Development has a significant impact on employee productivity of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.

VII. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

A. Population and Sampling Technique

This study uses a descriptive method where quantitative analysis has been conducted by collecting primary data from the respondents working in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. The population size of this study is the total number of employees working in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. Judgment (purposive) sampling has been used to select the respondents (Zikmund et al., 2010). Most of the respondents belong to different factories situated in Dhaka, Gazipur, Mawna and nearby areas. A structured questionnaire was prepared by consulting with some HR professionals and top management employees working in different RMG factories in Bangladesh. Questionnaires were distributed to 250 employees of different RMG factories. 195 respondents filled up the questionnaires and duly gave back out of which 178 questionnaires were found usable (N=178).

B. Questionnaire Design and Data Collection Tools

The dimensions of HRM practices such as Recruitment & Selection, HR Compliance, Compensation & Benefits, Performance Management, Employee Participation, and Training & Development were identified based on researchers own knowledge and discussions with some HR professionals and top management employees working in the RMG industry in Bangladesh.

The questionnaire was divided into 3 sections; section-A focuses on information about respondents' demographic descriptions (the summary of the section-A of the questionnaire is given in **Table 01**). Section-B of the questionnaire focuses on professional descriptions of the respondents (summary of the section-B of the questionnaire

is given in **Table 2**). Section is related to the dimensions of HRM practices (independent variables) and employee productivity (dependent variable). Demographic and professional data were analyzed using frequency and percentage. In the main segment, Pearson Correlation analysis was used to explore the significance of HRM practices on employee productivity in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. Apart from these, hypotheses of the study have been tested using Regression Analysis.

VIII. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Quantitative analysis approach has been used to analyze the data where SPSS Version 20.0 was used to perform correlation analysis and to test the hypotheses of the study. Following sub-sections (8.1 and 8.2) contain summary of the analysis of the study and detailed results have been shown in appendices (**Table 03 and 04**).

A. The Correlation Analysis

Table 03 shows the relationship between dependent and independent variables. The most significant correlation has been found between Compensation & Benefits and Employee Productivity with value .893 (.000). The second highest correlation has been explored between HR Compliance and Employee Productivity with value .698 (.000). Analysis shows the third highest correlation between Recruitment & Selection and Employee Productivity with value .594 (.000). Fourth, fifth and sixth significant correlations of Employee Productivity have been found with Employee Participation, Training & Development, and Performance Management with value .576 (.000), .561 and .512 (.000) consecutively.

B. The Regression Analysis

The hypotheses of the study have been tested using Regression Analysis (**Table 04**). H1 has been tested and was accepted with t-statistics 6.523 ($t > 2.5$) that shows significant positive relation between Recruitment & Selection and Employee Productivity. H2 was accepted with t-statistics 8.009 ($t > 2.5$) that shows significant positive relation between HR Compliance and Employee Productivity. H3 was accepted with t-statistics value 8.292 ($t > 2.5$) showing positive relation between Compensation & Benefits and Employee productivity. H4 has been accepted with t-statistics value 2.689 ($t > 2.5$) that indicates significant relation between Performance Management and Employee Productivity. H5 of the study shows a significant relationship between Employee Participation and Employee Productivity with t-statistics value 4.116 ($t > 2.5$) and has been accepted accordingly. The last hypothesis, H6, of the study has been accepted having t-statistics value 3.468 ($t > 2.5$) that shows significant relation between Training & Development and Employee Productivity

IX. CONCLUSIONS

This study has explored the impact of HRM practices on employee productivity in the RMG industry in Bangladesh. It explores that the HRM practices like Recruitment & Selection, HR Compliance, Compensation & Benefits, Performance Management, Employee Participation, and Training & Development) are significantly correlated with

employee productivity that has been analyzed using Pearson Correlation method. All of the hypotheses of the study have been tested using Regression Analysis and are accepted. However, this study finds the highest correlation between compensation & benefits and employee productivity. This reveals that still the employees in the RMG industry are financially focused. In this regard, the HR professionals and top management employees were interviewed again. They mentioned that the compensation package in the RMG industry is still under the average rate in the private sector in Bangladesh. Furthermore, HR compliance has been noted as the second highest influential factor in determining employee productivity where recruitment and selection is the third influential factor. The fourth, fifth and sixth influential factors influencing Employee Productivity are Employee Participation, Training & Development, and Performance Management consecutively.

The findings of this study will help the HR practitioners and other decision making persons in the RMG industry in Bangladesh to understand the significance of these HRM practices. They will be able to provide relative importance to the specific activities based on priority that will help their organizations to increase employee productivity that will ultimately lead to higher organizational performance. There are also future research indicators for the researchers in the area of human resource management. Future researchers may conduct research on the same topic based on other regions to check whether their studies give similar results or not. Besides this, they can also conduct study by modifying the research variables.

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APPENDICES

Table 1: Demographic Description

Description		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	121	67.98
	Female	57	32.02
Marital Status	Married	79	44.38
	Unmarried	92	51.69
	Divorced/Single Parent	07	3.93
Age	20-30	107	60.11
	30-40	43	24.16
	40-50	17	9.55
	50- Above	11	6.18

Table 2: Professional Description

Description		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Position	Top-level	13	7.30
	Mid-level	28	15.73
	Lower level	137	76.97
Educational Qualification	Below SSC	18	10.11
	SSC	67	37.64
	HSC	44	24.72
	Graduation	37	20.79
	Post Graduation	10	5.62
	M. Phil/PhD	02	1.12
Department	HR/Admin/Compliance	35	19.66
	Other Departments	143	80.34

Table 3: The Correlation Analysis

HR Practices	Particulars	Recruitment & Selection	HR Compliance	Compensation & Benefits	Performance Management	Employee Participation	Training & Development	Employee Productivity
Recruitment & Selection	Correlation	1	.421*	.591*	.671*	.685*	.513*	.594*
	Significance (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N-Value	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
HR Compliance	Correlation	.421*	1	.642*	.687*	.529*	.596*	.698*
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N-Value	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
Compensation & Benefits	Correlation	.591*	.642*	1	.584*	.671*	.589*	.893*
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N-Value	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
Performance Management	Correlation	.671*	.687*	.584*	1	.511*	.492*	.512*
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N-Value	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
Employee Participation	Pearson Correlation	.685*	.529*	.671*	.511*	1	.545*	.576*
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N-Value	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
Training & Development	Correlation	.513*	.596*	.589*	.492*	.545*	1	.561*
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000

	N-Value	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
Employee Productivity	Correlation	.594*	.698*	.893*	.512*	.576*	.561*	1
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N-Value	178	178	178	178	178	178	178

* Pearson Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4: Regression Analysis

SL	Hypotheses of the Study	t-statistics	Result
H1	Recruitment & Selection has a significant impact on employee productivity of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.	6.523	Accepted
H2	HR Compliance has a significant positive impact on employee productivity of RMG industry in Bangladesh.	8.009	Accepted
H3	Compensation & Benefits has a significant impact on employee productivity of RMG industry in Bangladesh.	8.292	Accepted
H4	Performance Management has a significant impact on employee productivity of RMG industry in Bangladesh.	2.689	Accepted
H5	Employee Participation has a significant impact on employee productivity of RMG industry in Bangladesh.	4.116	Accepted
H6	Training & Development has a significant impact on employee productivity of RMG industry in Bangladesh.	、	Accepted